

STATISTICS OF SHALLOW WATER, HIGH-FREQUENCY ACOUSTIC SCATTERING AND PROPAGATION

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Abstract - During August 1991, the Naval Research Laboratory conducted high-frequency shallow water acoustic scattering experiments in the Gulf of Mexico near Panama City, Florida. The acoustic measurements included surface and bottom reverberation, surface and bottom forward scattering, and direct path propagation. The results reported here are confined to the direct and bottom forward reflected paths and include the statistical characteristics of three signals; namely, the direct, the bottom reflected, and the direct plus the bottom reflected. Representative envelopes will be presented that illustrate the complexity of the shallow water environment. Statistics, including the means, variances, and probability distributions for each signal, are presented to discern any differences that can be exploited in the detection process. The frequency range covered during the experiment was from 20 to 180 kHz. The supporting environmental measurements included sound speed profiles, currents, wave heights, and bottom samples.

INTRODUCTION

A need exists for high-frequency acoustic measurements to support the safe operation of ships in shallow water. An understanding of the variability and statistical properties of direct and boundary-reflected acoustic signals in the shallow water environment is essential to the U.S. Navy. Statistical properties of high-frequency acoustic bottom reverberation have been reported by Chotiros *et al.* [1]. They found that the fluctuations followed a Rayleigh probability density function (PDF) for a widebeam receiver, but, for narrower beams, the PDF fit a log normal model. Stanic and Kennedy found that the distributions were not only dependent on beam width but also on frequency, range, and grazing angle for both a shell-covered sand bottom [2] and a smooth sand bottom [3]. McDaniel [4] has developed a model that predicts the beamwidth dependence reported by Chotiros *et al.*

This paper presents the results of the analysis of signals propagated along the direct path and forward scattered from the seafloor. Means, standard deviations, coefficients of

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variation, and probability distribution functions are presented as functions of frequency for the direct, direct plus the bottom reflected, and the bottom reflected signals.

EXPERIMENT

In August 1991, measurements of shallow water direct path propagation, bottom forward scatter, and bottom backscatter were made in the Gulf of Mexico 30 miles off the coast near Panama City, Florida. Two acoustic towers were carried on the deck of the HAWKE SEAL, an offshore oil field supply boat, to the site of the experiment, and lowered to the bottom. The water depth was 30 m and the range between the towers was 90 m. One tower was equipped for transmitting and receiving and the other for receiving only. Horizontal and vertical receiving arrays consisted of 16 hydrophones. Eight hydrophones were positioned along the horizontal array which was 7.6 m from the seafloor. The remaining 8 hydrophones were on the vertical array. Only data from Hydrophones 21, 22, and 24 on the horizontal array, and Hydrophones 25 and 27 on the vertical array have been analyzed for this paper. The positions and spacings of the hydrophones are given in Fig. 1. Two sources were used to generate signals between 20

Fig. 1. Hydrophone and source positions. Numbers next to the open characters indicate positions of each hydrophone on the forward scatter tower used in this report. Arrows on the axes indicate the structures extend beyond that shown. Other lines with arrow indicate distance from the array axes and between Hydrophones 22 and 24. The source locations on the backscatter tower are shown here for convenience.

and 180 kHz. Although they are located on the other tower, the backscatter tower, their positions are shown in Fig. 1. The center of the lower frequency source (20 to 90 kHz) was located about 15 cm below the horizontal array, and the center of the higher frequency source (90 to 180 kHz) was located adjacent to the other source about 10 cm below the horizontal array. For these measurements the maximum response axes of the sources were pointed at the arrays so the bottom was ensonified by off-axis portions of the main beam or by the side lobes. The signals used were 1.0-ms continuous wave pulses with a repetition rate of 1 sec.

A number of environmental parameters were measured in support of this experiment. These included sound speed profiles, currents, wave heights, and bottom sediments. The SANTA ROSA, a 33-m workboat assisted the HAWKE SEAL in diver operations, deployment of environmental sensors, deployment of anchors, and the collection of bathymetric data [5]. A representative sound speed profile is shown in Fig. 2. The two acoustic towers were deployed in an area characterized by sand ridges with an average RMS wave height of 0.5 cm.

ACOUSTIC DATA ANALYSIS

The output from each of the hydrophones was fed through a computer controlled variable gain amplifier, band shifted to 5 kHz, low pass filtered, and sampled at 20 kHz. The envelope derived from the time series has one sample every 0.1 millisecond. A typical example of this data is shown in Fig. 3. A total of 100 milliseconds of data was

Fig. 2. Sound speed profile from the Panama City 1991 Experiment.

Fig. 3. Envelope of representative received signal indicating paths of main arrivals.

collected from each hydrophone. The data contain signals from the direct and bottom reflected paths, as well as surface reflected paths.

This paper addresses the relative amplitude fluctuations for the direct and bottom bounce paths. Because of the geometry, their arrival times are separated by 0.9 ms as shown in Fig. 4. For this reason only short, 1-ms pulses are considered. The frequencies included in this report are 25, 40, 60, and 90 kHz from the low frequency transducer, and 90, 130, 150, and 180 kHz from the high frequency source. Table 1 shows the source beamwidths. For each of these configurations a 100-pulse data set was collected and analyzed.

Eight representative examples of time series envelopes for selected individual signals are shown in Fig. 5. They are characterized by fluctuations in amplitude that appear greater for a given pulse at different hydrophones than for different pulses for the same hydrophone. These trends are maintained for 100-pulse averages. Since the towers are stationary, the fluctuations observed must be due to multipath effects in the water column, or interference between the direct, bottom reflected, or subbottom scattered paths.

Each of the 100 pulses for each frequency starts at the same time relative to the time when the signal is transmitted (about sample number 560). Samples 562, 570, and 576 were chosen as representative of the direct, mixed, and bottom paths, respectively. Means, standard deviations, and coefficients of variation were calculated for these representative samples. The frequency dependence at Hydrophone 21 is shown in Fig. 6 and Fig 7. At 90 kHz mean values for the smaller source are larger than for the larger source for the direct and mixed paths. Because the error bars overlap, this may not be significant. Figure 8 shows the differences between hydrophones at the same frequency and time for direct and bottom reflected paths. Results for several hydrophones are given at 25 kHz to show the spatial variability of these statistics.

TABLE 1 BEAMWIDTHS AT SOURCE FREQUENCIES.

Frequency (kHz)	Source (cm)	-3dB Beamwidth (deg)
25	29.2	12.5
40	29.2	8.7
60	29.2	5.8
90	29.2	3.5
90	19	5.4
130	19	3.7
150	19	3.2
180	19	2.7

Fig. 4. Expanded view of the direct and bottom reflected arrivals from Figure 3 showing the overlapping portion

Means for the direct path range from 1.8 to 3.2 on the relative amplitude scale used. Corresponding standard deviations are between 0.36 and 0.57 and coefficients of variation are from 12 to 32%. The means for the portion of the data containing both direct and bottom bounce returns range from 1.2 to 3.5. Most of the standard deviations are a little higher but in the same range as for the direct path. Data representing only the bottom bounce path have mean values of 0.29 to 0.85. Standard deviations are between 0.13 and 0.49. Since the coefficient of variation is the standard deviation divided by the mean, lower mean values result in higher coefficients of variation that varied from 33 to 80% over the frequency range.

Histograms like those in Fig. 9 at 150 kHz show the distributions of the amplitudes for the three parts of the signal. A Rician probability density distribution for the mean and variance of the data is also shown [6]. A relatively simple way of testing the randomness of a process is to use the randomness factor, T, which is calculated using the equation: $T = \sqrt{v/(M^2 + v)}$ where v is the variance and M is the mean. Rician distributions with low T values are essentially Gaussian. Those with T values approaching 1.0 are Rayleigh [7]. Table 2 shows the T values derived from the statistics. Direct signals are Gaussian with the highest T value being 0.09. Bottom reflected signals are much more random, but with a randomness factor less than 0.4.

Fig. 5. Examples of variability in the time series plots with time, array position (hydrophone number) and frequency. The vertical axis is in relative amplitude units and the horizontal axis is time in sample number after the start of the data file for each pulse, with 0.1 ms time between samples, as in Fig. 4. Examples at the same frequency and pulse number were taken simultaneously at different phones. The three examples for hydrophone 25 were taken a few minutes apart at the same location.

Fig. 6. Frequency dependence of mean and standard deviation (shown by error bars) from 100 CW pulses received at Hydrophone 21. There are two sets of data at 90 kHz because both sources were used at that frequency.

Fig. 7. Coefficients of variation for Hydrophone 21: a) 29.2-cm source, and b) 19-cm source.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the analysis of data from five of the sixteen hydrophones, the following tentative conclusions can be drawn.

- The direct and mixed signal portions of the pulse contain relatively constant components of the signal as indicated by high mean values, low coefficients of variation, and low T values.

- For the direct path there is a dip in the mean value of the relative amplitude at 60 kHz for Hydrophone 21 and a slight broad peak at 130 kHz. The largest values for the standard deviation were at 60 kHz and 90 kHz (29.2 cm source). As a result of the low mean, the coefficient of variation peaks sharply at 60 kHz. At 90 kHz the mean for the 29.2 cm source was lower than for the 19-cm source resulting in a higher coefficient of variation for the larger source. It is speculated that phenomena occurring at 60 kHz

are due to the microthermal variations in the water column causing path length differences on the order of 2.5 cm.

- Similar results were obtained for the mixed region of the pulse where both the direct and bottom-reflected (lower levels than the direct) signals were present, except that the minimum mean value and the peak coefficient of variation shifted to 90 kHz.

- The sound speed data are not refined enough to indicate whether changes in the thermal microstructure are sufficient to explain the shift from 60 to 90 kHz.

Fig. 8. Spatial variability of direct and bottom signal statistics at 25 kHz: X Mean of direct path data with standard deviation shown by error bars, O Coefficient of variation for direct path, ∇ Mean of bottom path data with standard deviation, ◇ bottom path coefficient of variation.

- For the bottom-only portion of the signal, the mean values were much lower due to off-axis ensonification. They did not exhibit any pronounced frequency dependence, however, the coefficient of variation peaked very sharply at

Fig. 9. Histogram of data distribution overlaid with the scaled Rician probability distribution calculated from the data statistics.

Frequency (kHz)	Hydrophone	Table 2 Randomness Factor T		
		Direct	Mixed	Bottom
25	21	.03	.03	.20
	22	.03	.05	.15
	24	.04	.05	.22
	25	.04	.02	.23
	27	.02	.01	.18
40	21	.03	.02	.20
60	21	.09	.07	.38
90	21	.04	.20	.12
90	21	.01	.05	.12
130	21	.02	.02	.13
150	21	.01	.02	.09
180	21	.02	.03	.18

60 kHz. The bottom-only path is characterized by low means, high coefficients of variation, and higher T values indicative of more Rayleigh-like processes (randomness). The fluctuations must have been introduced within the water column, either by the thermal microstructure affecting the sound speed and the ensonified area, or by currents. These would account for random fluctuations in the direct path measurements as well.

- Larger variations were observed from hydrophone-to-hydrophone than from pulse-to-pulse for the same hydrophone. This indicates that interference effects from path length differences among the direct, bottom-reflected, and refracted paths through the bottom sediment are larger than those caused by fluctuations in the water column.

- For the data analyzed the direct and mixed paths follow a Gaussian distribution, while the bottom path is more Rayleigh.

- The sharp peaks in the coefficient of variation at 60 kHz and the different means and coefficients at 90 kHz for the two transducers will be investigated in experiments conducted in 1993.

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